

ROLE OF RASAYAN IN BALROG**Vd. Renuka S. Jambulkar¹, Vd. Sneha Tiwari^{2*}**¹Professor, Balroga Shri K. R. Pandav Ayurved College Nagpur.²Associate Professor, Kayachikista Shri K. R. Pandav Ayurved College Nagpur.***Corresponding Author: Vd. Sneha Tiwari**

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INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda suggested various modalities for the prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of pediatric diseases. This article emphasized preventive, diagnostic, and therapeutic approaches of Ayurveda for the management of Bal-Roga. Ancient ayurvedic literature reported the use of herbo-mineral formulations for the treatment of various childhood diseases. The use of Rasayana therapy in Bal Rog needs great attention towards the dosing and frequency to prevent any chances of adverse reactions. To enhance intelligence and immunity. The Rasayana Shashtra also involves the use of metallic formulation along with herbs. Guduchi, Shankhpushpi, Jyotishmati, Mandookparni. etc. are considered Rasayana. Rasayana boosts the functioning of Dhatus, Agni Srotasas, and Ojus and therefore acts as a rejuvenator. Ayurveda described Rasayana also for Bal-Rog, which can become harmful in children if not used properly. Rasayana therapy is also used as a preventive remedy in children since it enhances immunity and thus protects from various infectious diseases. There are various herbometalic formulations which may be used in children for different therapeutic purposes, such as Svaran Bhasm, Vacha, Madhu, Ghrita, Panchgavya Ghrita, Brahmi Ghrita, Abhaya Ghrita, Samvardhana Ghrita, Mandura Bhasma, and Lauha Bhasma, etc. Swama Prashan is a formulation of Swarna and herbs, Vacha, and Brahmi, along with honey and ghee, utilized for newborn baby to improve their immunity and mental health. Raw gold after rubbing on stone, along with a little amount of water, along with honey and ghee administered to the newborn baby. This type of formulation possesses Bal-Roga: Preventive Approaches. Stanya feeding from birth develops the immune system of Shishu; Stanya feeding is suggested by Ayurveda for newborn babies for Deha Pushti, Dhātu Vardhana, and Bala Vardhana. A light liquid diet may be given after 6-8 months; a heavy diet should be avoided, which may cause constipation. Ayurveda also advised Phalaprasana and Annaprashana Samsakara for Bala Avastha for proper physical and mental development. Ayurveda advocated that carbohydrates, protein, fat, minerals, and vitamins enriched Ahara boost the immunity of growing children; thus, food must encompass all essential components of a balanced diet.

Observation of body characters and movements of the suffering child, along with external symptoms. Consideration of the disease associated with the reproductive system of the mother and Dhatri. Graham Rogas plays a significant role in the disease pathogenesis in Bala Avastha. Other pathologic conditions, such as Beeja Dushti, Beejabhaga, Beejabhagavayava, are a few genital Vyadhi that may lead to pediatric diseases such as Khandoushtha, Kuchikarnika, Jatyandha, Suchimukhi, and Vaarta, etc. The diet regimen of the mother during the pregnancy period also plays a significant role in the Bal-Roga. Nadi-Pariksha and Sharir-Pariksha should be involved in diagnostic approaches. Prashna Pariksha also suggests some aspects about the history and prognosis of

the disease. Bal-Roga: Therapeutic Approaches Panchagavya Ghrita, Smriti Sagar Ras, Yogaraj Guggulu for Murcha. Shringi bhasma, Shwas kuthar ras, Talisadi Churna for Kasa. Vidangarishta, Krimikuthar ras, Vidanga Churna for Antajakrimi. Mushka Tailam, Changeri Ghrita for Guda bhramsha. Bhaskara Lavana Churna, Lavargodi Vati, Udarashula Lakshmvilas Ras for Pratishtyaya. Bhaskara Lavana Churna and Hingwashtak Churna for Udarashula. Rasayana therapy is a rejuvenator, to facilitate immunity, and as a memory enhancer. Herbs such as Shankhpushpi, Guduchi, Jyotishmati, Mandookparni, etc., improve Dhatus, Agni, Srotasas, and Ojus. Panchakarma therapy also plays a significant role in Bal Roga, since Panchakarma therapy

pacifies vitiated Doshas, performs detoxification, and opens Shrotas.

Virechana controls Pranavaha Sroto Vyadhi; Swasa Kasa when pitta dosha is vitiated. Nasya Karma helps in diseases that occur due to the Kapha and Vata predominance. Vamana eliminates Kapha Dosh by opening pranavaha srotastha. Many childhood diseases occur due to the vitiation of Doshas, and Panchkarma therapy helps to pacify these Doshas vitiation and thus relieve many disorders. It is believed that purification of the body through Panchkarma and Yoga pacifies Dosh and clears harmful toxins from the body, and thus helps to relieve many diseases in children. Panchkarma utilizes various approaches of Shodhana, such as Vamana, Virechan, and Nasya. Vamana in children helps to eliminate Kapha Dosh and thus opens pranavaha srotastha, which may be blocked due to the accumulation of Kapha in Kapha Vyadhi. Virechana may help in Pranavaha Sroto Vyadhi; Swasa Kasa, where pitta dosha is predominant. Nasya Karma is useful for diseases associated with Kapha and Vata predominance. Cerebral palsy is a common paediatric disorder in children. Seizures, hearing impairments, and intellectual disability are common features of diseases. Ayurveda emphasized various treatment options for diseases, including Panchkarma and yoga. It is Vata Vyadhi, which involves Pankshaghat, Ekangvata, Sarvagavata, Pangu, etc.

Ayurveda, the basic science of the traditional medical system in India, considers Bal Rog under Kaumarbhritya and mentions different therapies for the treatment of childhood diseases. Recently, many researchers have utilized Bala Panchakarma and Rasayana therapy for the management of various childhood diseases. This article describes various aspects of Bala Panchakarma and Rasayana therapy with special reference to childhood diseases. The literature suggested that Bala Panchakarma plays a significant role in the management of cerebral palsy. Pranavaha Srotasta and Tamaka Shwasa Panchakarma basically is a type of Shodhana Chikitsa. The basic principle of Kaumarabhritya involves Panchakarma in the late stage of development of Ayurveda science; however, fixation of drug dose and intensity of Bala Panchakarma is very important to prevent any side effects.

It is believed that Panchakarma, being Shodhana Chikitsa, removes vitiated Doshas. The various steps of Panchakarma, such as Vamana, Virechana Basti, Niruha or Yapana Bastis, and Anuvasana Basti recommended in early childhood for the management of different abnormal physiological conditions. Ayurveda believed that anti spastic, muscle-relaxant, and calming properties of Panchkarma and Yoga help in the management of cerebral palsy. Panchkarma and Yoga also emphasized the role of Pranavaha Srotaashta Vyadhi is a disease of Kapha Dosh. Kapha, along with Vata Dosh, plays a major role in the appearance of Panavaha Srotho Vyadhi, in which Dushitha Prana Vyau results in Hikka and

Swasa diseases. The condition involves aggravation of Kapha and Vyau Swasa, Kasa, and Hikka are the diseases of Prana Vahasroto Dusti. Ayurveda suggests the use of Panchakarma in pranavaha srotastha vyadhi not only to pacify kapha and vata Dosh, but it also helps in the excretion of harmful toxins. Shodhana through panchakarma clears accumulated Kapha and other secretions from the respiratory tract and thus relieves Pranavaha srotastha vyadhi.

REFERENCES

1. Susruta. Susurta Samhita with Nibandhasangraha Commentary by Dalhana, editors Acharaya YT, Acharaya Narayan R. Varanasi: Choukhambha Sanskrit Sanathan, 2003; 71.
2. Susruta. Susurta Samhita with Nibandhasangraha Commentary by Dalhana, editors Acharaya YT, Acharaya Narayan R. Varanasi: Choukhambha Sanskrit Sanathan, 2003.
3. Agnivesha. Charaka Samhita with Ayurvedadipika Commentary by Chakarpanidatta, editor Acharya YT. Varanasi: Choukhambha Orientalia, 2001; 1.
4. Sulochana, Basic Concepts of Kaumarabhritya (Bala Roga), RA Journal of Applied Research, 2015; 10: 378.
5. Kumar MA, Ojha NK, Kumar A. Rationality of Swarna Prashan in Pediatric Practice. International Journal of Ayurvedic and Herbal Medicine, 2013; 3: 1191-1200. PEDIATRIC MANAGEMENT Prophylactic Approaches Diagnosis of Disease Therapeutic Approaches J Ayu Herb Med, January-March 2017; 3(1).
6. Kumar A, Garai AK. A clinical study on Pandu Roga, iron deficiency anemia, with Trikatrayadi Lauha suspension in children. Journal of Ayurveda & Integrative Medicine, 2012; 3(4): 215-222.
7. Pravin M, Vedika A, Patel KS, Kori VK, Rajagopala S. An Evidence Based Review on Ayurvedic Management of Tamaka Shwasa (Bronchial Asthma), Int J Ayur Pharma Research, 2015; 3(2): 11-18.